

Urban Cholula Salvage Archaeological Geodatabase: White Paper

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The National Endowment for the Humanities, Humanities Collections and Reference Resources “Foundations” Grant supported the initial development of the Urban Cholula Salvage Archaeological Geodatabase (UCSAG), which is associated with archaeological collections from the last 2,000 years in the Cholula area of Puebla, Mexico. The Cholula collections enable researchers to tell the story of the rich Mexican Indigenous history before, during, and after Spanish colonialism. The site of Cholula is world-renowned, drawing over half a million visitors per year, yet visits are often limited to the Great Pyramid rather than its larger footprint, Urban Cholula, now covered by the modern cities of San Pedro Cholula and San Andrés Cholula. The collections from Urban Cholula, discovered through various salvage excavations in these two cities, have the potential to transform understandings of how Cholula operated as a political and religious center during the pre-Columbian era, and continued to be a resilient locus of Mesoamerican culture throughout the colonial period, remaining so today. UCSAG-Foundations designed a geodatabase and determined the protocols to bring the attention of the world to these little-known, but incredibly significant humanities collections. Collaborating with Mexican archaeologists and INAH, the Instituto Nacional de Antropología e Historia in Mexico, the Center for Advanced Spatial Technologies at the University of Arkansas began designing a database and workflow that would be open-source, compliant with INAH standards, and incorporate the many fields and data types associated with the excavation. Indirectly, the UCSAG-Foundations project engaged with the issue of “dark data” that many archaeologists and museum professionals face today: archaeological collections are obtained for “salvage” purposes (when an area is unavoidably destroyed for development), which are less frequently published and often excluded from museum exhibits. UCSAG-Foundations might serve as a model to other projects around the world struggling to find guidance on FOSS (free and open-source software) platform solutions for making their data more widely available and accessible.

The UCSAG-Foundations project members collaboratively produced a number of documents specific for the Cholula project but valuable to archaeologists around the world who struggle to digitize and manage spatial data in a long-term sustainable way. The sections that follow are intended to provide guidance and examples of how to approach archaeological data, including legacy data, in a way that helps standardize and combine disparate sites, datasets, and collection and cataloguing methods into a single database structure.

Section 1 details the salvage projects involved, overall goals for the geodatabase, and intended audience and outreach. Less than half of these projects (23 of 58 excavations carried out between 2005-2022) have been completed to the reporting stages. **Section 2** expands this objective by explaining how structured data stored within a geodatabase allows the generation of more nuanced interpretations of the life of the Cholultecas (those who lived in Cholula) in the past. Visualizations in a Geographic Information System (GIS) permit an analysis of the spatial patterning of artifacts and populations over time, encouraging a holistic view of Urban Cholula rather than individual isolated excavation projects. Finally, the geodatabase will serve as a standard for archaeological mitigation work both in Cholula and in other areas of the State of Puebla.

Section 3 discusses two options for building archaeological database: a top-down or a bottom-up approach. The top-down approach proceeds by first creating a geodatabase based on years of experience with data categories and possibilities; database structure, vocabulary, and standards are established at the outset according to international best practices. Proprietary (paid) option best suited for archaeology

include ArcGIS Pro (and StoryMaps), and the FOSS options include QGIS, the Archaeological Recording Kit (ARK), and Omeka S. The bottom-up approach meets ongoing archaeological projects in the state they are in, in a more piecemeal process. The database is built according to data categories that already exist in paper-based forms or digital spreadsheets; data can be added, edited, and queried, with vocabulary and other standards developed later. If the database includes geographic coordinates, it can be imported to a GIS for spatial analysis. Proprietary (paid) relational database options include Microsoft Access and FileMaker Pro. FOSS options include SQLite, MySQL, PostgreSQL (with PostGIS). Ultimately our Mexican collaborators and we decided on a bottom-up process, using QGIS, PostgreSQL, and LibreOffice for data entry. **Section 4** describes the metadata standards and requirements for the UCSAG database in order for the project to be in alignment with INAH protocols. It importantly identifies the CIDOC-CRM model that is most relevant to the project, “el Modelo de Datos México,” and INAH’s document that defines the metadata standards appropriate for the project, “Norma Técnica para la elaboración de Metadatos Geográficos (NTM).” Incorporating these guidelines makes the database usable and comparable by multiple entities in Mexico and beyond. **Section 5** follows with the data acquisition protocols developed for the UCSAG dataset, including for both spatial and non-spatial data.

Section 1: Report on the Status of the Archaeological Projects Carried Out in San Pedro and San Andrés Cholula between 2005 and 2022

Between 2005 and 2022, 58 archaeological rescue projects were commissioned to archaeologist Carlos Cedillo Ortega, affiliated with the INAH Puebla Regional Center, and are in different stages of execution and development.

Of the 58 projects, 50 were carried out, and 23 of have satisfactorily concluded all phases, i.e., field work, material analysis, and reports. In ten projects, field activities and material sorting were completed, but the final technical reports were not produced. In five projects, field activities and partial material analysis were carried out, and therefore there are no final technical reports. On the other hand, there are 12 projects that only carried out fieldwork and further processes were left unfinished.

The main problem of four (Collections of the 12th, S-01, S-09 and S-13) of the 12 projects that were only carried out in their field phase, is that complex contexts relevant to the cultural history of Cholula were excavated. Due to this complexity, excavation work was lengthened and the budgets for lab work also lagged. The excavated contexts were sets of more than 100 individuals buried and/or cremated, generally accompanied by ceramic and lithic offerings. In two cases, there were architectural ensembles associated with the burial areas, also with a variety of construction elements from floors, walls, and hearths to large platforms for residential or ceremonial use. Of the remaining eight projects, six present elements such as burials, construction elements, and garbage dumps with fewer materials but with important information about the neighborhoods of the ancient city of Cholula. The study of the skeletal remains of one of the projects with the largest number of excavated burials has been concluded with the support of a Master’s thesis and the University of Arizona through Dr. James Watson. However, the rest of the ceramic and lithic materials are still waiting to be studied, totaling 1,664 bags. It is worth mentioning that Cholula is one of the archaeological sites in Mexico from which the most ceramic material is obtained in excavations.

In three of the projects with a partial analysis of the materials, different contexts were excavated with burials, water wells with animal remains not found in other contexts, and truncated conical wells. In addition to spaces with architecture that include floor levels from pre-Hispanic to colonial contexts,

ancient roads, walls, slopes, steps, and hearths may correspond to periods between the Classic to the Late Postclassic. The completion of the classification of the materials will allow the necessary information to be gathered to be able to establish the relationships between variables and interpret past lifeways.

Regarding the ten projects in which the final technical reports are missing, it is necessary to review the information available, in some cases there are partial field or laboratory reports, in others the field drawings have not yet been digitized or have not been edited to be integrated into the reports. The integration of the final technical reports allows the information to be organized and endorsed by the INAH for future research.

Regardless of the relevance or particularity of the archaeological contexts in each of the projects, the works that could be considered more modest often provide new information about the area through potsherds, skeletal remains, animal artifacts, lithic artifacts and other materials collected, which are sometimes unique specimens in the Cholula area. These materials can tell us about the animal species with which they had contact, exchange between different areas of the country, or customs and fashions of the different neighborhoods of the city.

In principle, the database that is intended to be built with the support of CAST of the University of Arkansas will make it possible to streamline the organization of the information for cataloguing and the production of the final technical reports. In the background, the database will allow us to visualize the relationships between different variables and excavation spaces to investigate the processes of development of the Cholultecas over time. And finally, the reflection of this accumulation of information obtained through seventeen years of work and organized with the proposed digital tool will lead to new research questions to delve into the daily life of Cholula in its past times.

Section 2: Summary of the Investigative Functions of the Geographic Database for Archaeological Salvage and Rescue Projects in the Urban Area of Cholula

The objectives set for the use of the database are, in the first instance, as a repository to catalog and investigate the data generated by the Salvge and Rescue Projects directed by Archaeologist Carlos Cedillo Ortega, Professor – Researcher at the National Institute of Anthropology and History (INAH), and his work team between 2005 and 2022. During this period, important excavation work was carried out that allowed the development of a specific work methodology, achieving the standardization of the data recovered in the field. This data structure was generated with the aim of forming a geographic database that allows us to know and interpret in a more complete way some aspects of the life of the Cholultecas in the past.

The correct structuring and capture of information within the database will allow the generation of visualizations in the form of cartographic maps accompanied by explanatory texts and tables showing the location and archaeological information obtained for each of the Projects carried out by means of a GIS. These visualizations can be generated by the project's researchers from interactions with different data groups contained in the various modules. Information about excavated contexts, elements recorded, and objects and artifacts recovered are included in a structured way, allowing the researchers of the project to identify the correlations that exist between them.

The use of GIS visualizations will facilitate the characterization of each of the excavated contexts, allowing the identification of spatial and chronological patterns such as the spatial and temporal distribution of the different archaeological materials recorded. The results obtained from the analysis of

the different materials and archaeological contexts recovered will allow us to address questions about their manufacture, use, and reasons for their final discard. Additionally, the structuring of data related to the human skeletal remains, through a detailed study of the osteobiographical characteristics of the individuals recovered during the excavations, will allow us to know more about the biological profile, as well as some aspects of the lifestyle of the ancient population of Cholula and its changes over time. Likewise, an adequate characterization and classification of the built architectural elements that could be identified and recorded during the excavations will increase knowledge about the use of the spaces explored, as well as the techniques, methods, and construction styles that were used at different times in the ancient history of Cholula.

By means of these cartographic visualizations and the identification of chronological and spatial patterns, it will be possible to carry out a comparative analysis of the different excavated contexts, reaching a larger scale of spatial and temporal analysis for the study of the ancient city of Cholula. The diachronic analysis of each of the intervened contexts will facilitate the identification of changes in the patterns of distribution and frequency of archaeological materials, as well as variations in the biological profile and lifestyle of the population of the city of Cholula over time, considering the urban area of Cholula as a whole as the unit of analysis. Moreover, user-generated visualizations can be adapted to be used in technical reports, academic publications, and other dissemination products, contributing to more efficiently communicating archaeological information generated by salvage and rescue work.

Finally, this database is intended to serve as a standard for archaeological mitigation work, both in the city of Cholula and in other areas of the State of Puebla. This is thanks to the adaptability of the different modules that compose it, allowing an internal control of the information for the exclusive use of the INAH, as well as an efficient management of archaeological data from its collection to its interpretation. By having a repository of archaeological data obtained from salvage and rescue work in the city of Cholula, it will be easier to integrate the information generated with other archaeological research, thus complementing the corpus of data available to know the ancient history of Cholula.

Examples for the development of the geographic database for Archaeological Salvage and Rescue of the Urban Area of Cholula:

- 1.- Catalhoyuk living archive <http://catalhoyuk.stanford.edu/>
- 2.- Endangered Archaeology in the Middle East and North Africa EAMENA <https://database.eamena.org/>
- 3.- The Strategic Environmental Archaeology Database SEAD <https://www.sead.se/>
- 4.- The Digital Archaeological Archive of Comparative Slavery DAACS <https://www.daacs.org>
- 5.- Single Public Registry System of Monuments and Archaeological and Historical Zones SURPMZAH <https://registropublico.inah.gob.mx/>

Section 3: Geospatial Database Options

There are a number of databases that can support spatial archaeological information, either natively or through a plugin (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Spatial_database#Geodatabase). Some specifically target archaeology and cultural heritage, while others are intended as open-access repositories for any type of digital data. Most of those targeting the archaeology sector are designed for use on mobile devices at the trowel's edge, through to artifact analysis, and finally publication and dissemination. The summary below gives a brief overview of the most relevant paid and open-source geodatabase management systems for

the Urban Cholula Archaeological Salvage and Rescue Project. Most of these databases were developed and are currently maintained on servers in Europe, predominantly the UK. Here, we focus on evaluating whether and to what extent each geodatabase can integrate ancient Cholula's architecture and artifact classes, and ability to access and share these data once entered.

Option 1: Geospatial Databases

The first option toward building a geospatial database starts from the top-down. In this model, an optimal database structure, vocabulary, and standards are established from the outset of an archaeological project. Data are "born digital," input as the project proceeds over time, making paper- or spreadsheet-based forms unnecessary. This model requires significant time, knowledge, experience, and foresight to design (and inevitably tweak) and implement before data collection begins; it also involves active GNSS receivers (or known coordinates) at the field site. This top-down model would function best for new archaeological projects in areas where the designer has deep familiarity with data types; all non-necessary paperwork would be eliminated, and data would simply be entered as it is excavated. Difficulties include managing a server for multiple users and continuous updating, and, in the case of Cholula, the tedious process of digitization and data entry must be completed, in some cases, long after excavations have concluded. The most popular proprietary geodatabase is Esri's ArcGIS Pro, and the open-source alternative is QGIS. Two additional open-source relational databases with geolocation capabilities include ARK and Omeka S.

Licensing or fee required:

[ESRI ArcGIS Pro](#) is the current industry standard GIS software. Arc Pro allows data integration from multiple sources, simultaneous visual display in 2D and 2.5D, data editing and analysis, workflow automation, and work sharing through web services or digital/paper prints. Two relevant associated programs include [ArcGIS Online](#), interactive web mapping software, and [StoryMaps](#), to tell stories using GIS-based maps on a user-friendly website (which requires data be published to ArcGIS Online). Though the University of Arkansas maintains extensive licensing for enterprise, desktop, and online versions, student and personal licenses have been USD \$100/year for the past decade, perhaps making the software affordable into the future. While the StoryMaps feature would easily translate the ArcGIS geodatabase into a public-facing website, data would not necessarily be downloadable for other researchers, and website creation would need time and intention.

Examples and Explanations:

Alemy, Alexis et al. 2017. Creating a User-Friendly Interactive Resources with ESRI's ArcGIS StoryMap Program. *Historical Archaeology* 51(2):288-297. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/10.2307/48700090>

Howland, Matthew D. et al. 2020. Integrating Digital Datasets into Public Engagement through ArcGIS StoryMaps. *Advances in Archaeological Practice* 8(4):351-360. DOI:10.1017/aap.2020.14

Examples: <https://doc.arcgis.com/en/arcgis-storymaps/gallery/>

Free and Open-Source Software (FOSS)

"[QGIS](#) is a professional GIS application that is built on top of and proud to be itself Free and Open Source Software (FOSS)." Similarly to ArcGIS, QGIS allows data viewing and exploration; the creation, manipulation, analysis, and exportation of data; mapmaking and cartography; and publication to the internet via QGIS Server. Over 500 plugins are also available for extended features, such as working with SQL and databases (DB Manager), georeferencing, and an integrated Python console. Extensive

documentation, free step-by-step tutorials on QGIS for archaeology, and a large user-developer community also exist. Overall, because QGIS is open-source and customizable, it can be less stable/compatible and simple tasks may take more mouse clicks. ArcGIS has more built-in features and options but is also more rigid, giving users less control.

[ARK \(Archaeological Recording Kit\)](#) “is a web-based ‘toolkit’ for the collection, storage and dissemination of archaeological data. It includes data-editing, data-creation, data-viewing and data-sharing tools, all of which are delivered using a web-based front-end.” It has been particularly successful for the practice of a digital archaeology that is more reflexive, open, and participatory (Morgan and Eve 2012). With this application, data could be made available immediately, as soon as it is entered into the database, allowing researchers and the public access (and input) as the project continues (rather than only at its completion). It is multi-user as well as multi-lingual, with customization available for intermediate and advanced users. Mapping is an advanced feature. Because this database has been in use for various projects for over a decade, there is an ample community for Q&A and troubleshooting.

Examples/Explanations:

Morgan, Colleen and Stuart Eve. 2012. DIY and Digital Archaeology: What Are You Doing to Participate? *World Archaeology* 44(4): 521-537. DOI: 10.1080/00438243.2012.741810

“[Omeka S](#) is a next generation web publishing platform for institutions interested in connecting digital cultural heritage collections with other resources online.” Similarly to ARK, it is highly customizable, and users can install Neatline or the Mapping Module to geolocate items and add interactive maps. Omeka uses the Dublin Core Metadata Initiative and can be aligned with other international thesauri and ontologies. The system also allows uploading of photos and 3D models, including interoperability with 3DHOP.

Examples/Explanations:

<https://archaeo.peercommunityin.org/articles/rec?id=341>

Athanassopoulos, Effie et al. 2017. UNL Campus Archaeology: Building Digital Resources. *CHNT22*. chrome-extension://efaidnbmnnnibpcajpcglclefindmkaj/https://www.chnt.at/wp-content/uploads/eBook_CHNT22_Athanassopoulos_.pdf

Toscano, Maurizio, Manuel J. Cobo, and Enrique Herrera-Viedma. 2022. Soluciones software para sistemas de información web en humanidades digitales: revisión, análisis y estudio comparativo. *Profesional de la Información* 31(2): <https://doi.org/10.3145/epi.2022.mar.11>

Whalen, Zach. 2019. Teaching with Objects: Individuating Media Archaeology in Digital Studies. *Journal of Interactive Technology and Pedagogy*, no. 15. <https://cuny.manifoldapp.org/read/teaching-with-objects-individuating-media-archaeology-in-digital-studies-99653a5a-7f07-4529-beb8-c4cb11c944bc/section/be846af9-25b6-4dbd-9804-af481194882d>

Option 2: Relational Database Management Systems (RDBMS)

A second major option to build an archaeological geodatabase starts from the bottom-up. In this model, a simple relational database is created for the immediate input of archaeological information, at the trowel’s edge or from paper- or spreadsheet-based forms (as in the case of Cholula). Data can be added, edited, and queried. Vocabulary can, but does not have to, conform to international standards. Later, if the database contains geographic coordinates, it can be imported into a GIS for spatial analysis. Vocabulary can also be later updated for import into a comparative archaeological data repository.

[Microsoft Access](#) [paid], available for use on Windows machines, is a basic single-user database with relational capabilities. Access uses a dialect of SQL (see below) for queries and provides a tool for creating forms for data entry. If coordinate data are included in the database, it can be linked to maps in Arc Pro or in QGIS. Many archaeological projects use MS Access, though publication and sharing of the data are limited unless the Access file is made available online. Access must be purchased with the Microsoft 365 Suite, currently at \$70/yr for a single computer.

[FileMaker Pro](#) [paid] is a cross-platform relational database with Server and iOS (not Android) capabilities. In comparison to Access, FMP's built-in database templates, layout themes, and user interface are easier and faster to learn. Server capabilities allow multiuser access and granular security options (restricted access to particular databases, layouts, or fields, etc.). Tablet or mobile fieldwork app (FileMaker Go) is only supported for iOS (iPad or iPhone). Many archaeological projects also use FileMaker Pro. (In the past, Access was mostly utilized by Windows-users, and FileMaker by Mac-users.) There are many versions of FMP, and earlier versions of files cannot always be opened by newer versions of the software. The filename extensions are also proprietary, and can only be opened by FileMaker, making a subscription necessary to revisit old data. However, all data can be exported as CSV files or a spreadsheet. As of 2023, a single user perpetual educational license is \$299. A perpetual license for FileMaker Server with five users for 12 months is \$3000 (their minimum).

In contrast to MS Access or FileMaker, most open-source relational databases use SQL (Structured Query Language), a programming language designed to access, manipulate, define, and control access to data stored within databases. Originally developed by IBM in the 1970s, SQL is now used by most organizations that collect and store data and is thus widespread and versatile. SQL standards are maintained by the American National Standards Institute (ANSI), the International Organization for Standardization (ISO), and the International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC), though various dialects exist that support more complex operations than standard SQL. Some of the major dialects of SQL include:

- [SQLite](#) [free] is the most popular and simplest relational database. It does not need servers or administrators to manage the server; as a single file, it is small, easy to share, and requires little memory. It is often combined with Python or R (open-source programming languages) for greater usefulness. However, because there is no server, there may be only one user, and only this user may make changes at a time. In other words, SQLite cannot accommodate multiple users or differential levels of access.
 - o Tutorial with demo data: <https://datacarpentry.org/sql-socialsci/>
- [MySQL](#) [free] is an open-source relational database management system, originally offered commercially by Oracle. It has a client-server architecture, requiring one centralized server and multiple clients (or individual users) that can access the server through a username and password. As the most popular version of SQL, there is exhaustive documentation and resources online for building and maintaining a MySQL database. There are also a variety of Graphic User Interface (GUI) options. The two main disadvantages of MySQL include a sacrifice of full SQL compliance for speed and ease of use (and so it lacks support for some functionalities), and its status as dual-license software, privileging the paid version.
 - o [Home | BIAD \(biadwiki.org\)](#)
- [PostgreSQL](#) [free] describes itself as “the most advanced open-source relational database in the world.” It adheres most closely to SQL standards, and there is ample official documentation and

the open-source community for further development, training, and troubleshooting. Of import here, PostgreSQL supports the popular add-on [PostGIS](#), a geospatial database extender that allows storing, indexing, and querying geospatial data. Many major archaeological databases for public now use PostgreSQL on the backend.

- <https://www.sead.se/database/>
- <https://www.daacs.org/about-the-database/database-structure/>
- [MS SQL Server](#) [paid] is Microsoft's (MS) commercially available relational database management system, designed for Windows. SQL Server Express is a free version of this software, but only supports up to 10 GB of data and local (not networked) connections.

Other: Archaeological Data Repositories/Archives

The following two options—Open Context and tDAR—are usually considered repositories rather than relational databases. However, Open Context does have a web interface for spatial data exploration. They are also both meant for sharing data *after* the project has been completed, rather than during excavation or laboratory analysis. [Zenodo](#) is another digital data repository for open science from every discipline, allowing up to 50 GB of uploaded files. Nonetheless, they are discussed here as both a more inclusive review of what is currently available and popular, and as additional venues to improve data shareability. Both also offer (paid) support for data upload, cleaning, metadata standardization, and publication.

“Archives are specifically designated spaces for the management and long-term retention and retrieval of information. Digital archives are designed to house extensive metadata, create routines to check file status, maintain robust backup procedures, and implement security and access measures, ensuring data integrity and long-term viability” (Nicholson et al. 2023, 65).

- Nicholson, Christopher, Sarah Kansa, Neha Gupta, and Rachel Fernandez. 2023. Will It Ever Be FAIR? Making Archaeological Data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable. *Advances in Archaeological Practice* 11(1): 63-75.

[Open Context](#) “publishes digital datasets—structured (often tabular) data, images, maps, field notes, 3D models, etc.” Rather than a do-it-yourself model, users work with an editorial team that supports the transfer, cleaning, annotation, and even peer-review and archiving of submitted data. Their overall goal is to make data more accessible and provide a solid foundation for future data integration. Data are accessible through a basic web interface, which includes a map. Most data are from the Middle East, and the system was developed and is maintained in Europe. Cost depends on the size of the dataset, accounting for images, documents, GIS layers, and other media (including 3D models).

Examples and Explanations:

Kansa, Eric C. and Sarah Witcher Kansa. 2010. Publishing Data in Open Context: Methods and Perspectives. *The CSA Newsletter* XIII(2): September. <https://csanet.org/newsletter/fall10/nlf1001.html>

[The Digital Archaeological Record \(tDAR\)](#) is an international digital repository for any and all records emanating from archaeological projects. Users may upload their own data and metadata, or work with a tDAR staff member for upload. It is endorsed and supported by the Society for American Archaeology and Society for Historical Archaeology. Data are accessible through a simple download. The system was developed and is currently housed at Arizona State University, with most data from North America inclusive of Cholula. The cost is \$20/file for under 100 files, or \$10/file for over 100 files, at a max of 50 MB per file.

Examples/Explanations:

<https://www.digitalantiquity.org/publications/>

Comparison of Open Context vs. tDAR:

Sheehan, Beth. 2015. Comparing Digital Archaeological Repositories: tDAR Versus Open Context. *Behavioral & Social Sciences Librarian* 34(4):173-213. DOI: 10.1080/01639269.2015.1096155

Additional Resources for Building an Archaeological Geodatabase

Heritage Data – Vocabularies ([Vocabularies | Heritage Data](#))

Ariadne – Interoperability Slideshow ([PowerPoint Presentation \(archaeologydataservice.ac.uk\)](#))

- The most widely used ontology in Cultural Heritage is the CIDOC CRM, which is an ISO standard
 - o Not specific to archaeology, so extensions have been developed like the CRM-EH and CRMarcheo
- Top-down (using a controlled vocabulary to map data) vs. bottom-up (build a vocabulary specific to an area from individual projects)
- Linked Data and Linked Open Data (LOD), which is not a relational database but a graph data structure (without a hierarchy)
- “Portals” are the frontend for querying interoperable data

The Open Digital Archaeology Textbook (ODATE) - <https://o-date.github.io/>

- Making data useful into the future is called making your data “future-proof” (p. 45)
- “A relational database consists of many different tables connected together with *relationships* that tell computers how things fit together” p. 63

Internet Archaeology - <https://intarch.ac.uk/issues/index.html>

- Issue 58 (2021) & Issue 63 (2023): Digital Archiving in Archaeology, Parts I and II
 - o Un resumen, país por país, del estado de la arqueología en formato digital
- Other Issues que discuten bases de datos y la organización de datos digitales

Advances in Archaeological Practice - [Advances in Archaeological Practice: Volume 11 - Issue 1 | Cambridge Core \(2023\)](#)

- Klehm, Carla. “The Use and Challenges of Spatial Data in Archaeology”
<https://doi.org/10.1017/aap.2022.38>
 - o Habla del ciclo de vida de datos espaciales, desde su colección hasta que se publiquen, y nuevos desarrollos con datos grandes (Big Data), estandarización, accesibilidad, y utilidad.
- Ortman, Scott and Jeffrey Altschul. “What North American Archaeology Needs to Take Advantage of the Digital Data Revolution” <https://doi.org/10.1017/aap.2022.42>

- Pregunta que se necesita para la integración de datos arqueológicos de varios proyectos salvamentos. En los EEUU, “cultural resource management” es la arqueología de salvamento y rescate; como en Cholula, hay muchos proyectos individuos, pero no son conectados, y los datos no se comunican entre sí.
- Gutpa, Neha, Andrew Martindale, Kisha Supernant, and Michael Elvidge. “The CARE Principles and the Reuse, Sharing, and Curation of Indigenous Data in Canadian Archaeology.” <https://doi.org/10.1017/aap.2022.33>
 - Habla de los principios CARE (beneficios Colectivos, Autoridad para controlar, Responsabilidad, y Ética) y la gestión de datos arqueológicos por gente Indígena en Canadá, hacia un reconocimiento de los derechos de la gente Indígena en tomar decisiones sobre su propio patrimonio.
- Nicholson, Christopher, Sarah Kansa, Neha Gupta, and Rachel Fernandez. “Will It Ever Be FAIR? Making Archaeological Data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable.” <https://doi.org/10.1017/aap.2022.40>
 - Los autores discuten los principios FAIR y CARE en el contexto de la arqueología en los EEUU y Canadá. No es solamente un esfuerzo por los arqueólogos, sino que también uno que debe ser parte de los principios básicos de organizaciones profesionales, publicadores, archivados de datos, y políticas de agencias gubernamentales.
- Halford, Kirk F. and Dayna M. Ables. “The National Cultural Resources Information Manage System (NCRIMS): New Horizons for Cultural Resources Data Management and Analyses” <https://doi.org/10.1017/aap.2022.39>
 - Presentan una nueva iniciativa de una rama del gobierno de los EEUU que organiza y estandariza los datos de proyectos arqueológicos de salvamento y de rescate, a través de 11 diferentes estados en el oeste del país. Es una base de datos basada en el web, que utiliza un SIG con servidores.

Advances in Archaeological Practice - [Volume 12 - Special Issue 1 - February 2024](#)

- Domeischel, Jenna y S. Terry Childs “A Collections-Based View of the Future of Archaeology” <https://doi.org/10.1017/aap.2023.37>
 - La introducción al issue. Habla de la preservación y gestión de datos digitales en la arqueología a través de diferentes sectores (salvamento, rescate, investigación, federal, privado, el público, estudiantes, etc.)
 - Cofield, Sara Rivers, S. Terry Childs, y Teresita Majewski. “A Survey of How Archaeological Repositories Are Managing Digital Associated Records and Data” <https://doi.org/10.1017/aap.2023.29>
 - Neller, Angela, Jasmien Heckman, Elizabeth Bollwerk, Kelsey Noack Myers, and Josh Wells. “Making Archaeological Collections More Findable and Accessible through Increased Coordination” <https://doi.org/10.1017/aap.2023.31>
 - Austin, Anne, Ixchel Faniel, Brittany Brannon, y Sara Kansa. “Improving the Usability of Archaeological Data through Written Guidelines.” <https://doi.org/10.1017/aap.2023.38>

- Gencheva, Veronika. “From data collection to analysis: Designing a relational database for archaeological research in the eastern Rhodope region” doi:10.57573/be-ja.13.99-114
 - o Un ejemplo de construir una base de datos geoespacial para datos espaciales y no espaciales, y demostración de un análisis espacial, en una región de Bulgaria.

Section 4: Metadata Considerations for the Urban Cholula Database

Metadata is information about digital data (computer files) whose main purpose is to achieve digital preservation and give context to the information contained therein. They are defined by a document that identifies the content that must be provided to describe geospatial resources and archaeological data in digital format. This document known as the “metadata standard” defines how the data was collected and for what purpose, and seeks to achieve complete standardization of information necessary to facilitate interoperability with other systems. The standardization of information in turn allows data to be easily searched and found online, making its consultation, analysis, and control more accessible.

For this, there are documents that guide best practices at a global level and that help standardize geographic data (ISO 19115:2014), and cultural heritage data (ISO 21127:2023) regardless of the place or time period of the information they represent. . For Mexico, a data model compatible with the ISO 21127:2023 standard derived from the CIDOC-CRM data model has been developed; the Mexico Data Model (MDM). This model, developed specifically to be implemented in “Mexicana, Repository of the Cultural Heritage of Mexico” (<https://mexicana.cultura.gob.mx/es/repositorio/modelo-datos>), a platform whose objective is to link collections protected by the Ministry of Culture and its administrative units and decentralized bodies.

The current rules and regulations on metadata that govern Cultural Heritage in Mexico establish clear metadata standards that seek to achieve data preservation and interoperability between systems. The National Institute of Statistics, Geography and Informatics (INEGI) has established the “Technical Standard for the preparation of Geographic Metadata (NTM)”, a metadata standards document for spatial data creators that establishes the minimum provisions for the preparation of metadata of geographic data groups of national interest or that serve to generate these, carried out by the State Units that make up the System, either by themselves or by third parties, as well as promoting their harmonization and homogeneity (Article One). In the development of said document, it was sought to comply with the ISO 19115 standard, although in a simplified manner, based on what was specified in its core, leaving only fundamental elements. Additionally, a “Methodological Guide for the Generation and Integration of Geographic Metadata was developed in accordance with the Technical Standard for the preparation of Geographic Metadata (NTM)”. This guide is a document that describes the elements of NTM, the criteria and considerations for each, as well as offering an example that clarifies its objective, to achieve the same interpretation and a common result.

The Ministry of Culture has developed Metadata Standards in the document “Technical guidelines for the preparation of metadata in matters of Culture” which seeks to be a guide for the standardization of the preparation and presentation of metadata belonging to the cartographic information of each agency that it is part of the Ministry of Culture, ensuring that the data is compatible with each other and understandable for any user. Likewise, Institutional metadata standards have been developed within the INAH, published as part of the “Operation guidelines for the digitization of cultural assets and classification of digital

objects in the INAH” (2016). This document identifies the minimum metadata types and fields to maintain control of the digital objects safeguarded by the institute. Three types of metadata necessary for good management of digital data and allowing their interoperability are identified, in addition to indicating whether these should be mandatory (O), conditional (C), or optional (Opt). Descriptive Metadata has eight fields of information:

1. Title
2. Authorship
3. Subject or theme of the cultural object or good
4. Description
5. Date
6. Place
7. Format
8. Identifier

These fields are basic for the description and depending on the cultural asset, those that are necessary may be added, taking international and national cartographic rules as a reference.

Digital Preservation Metadata has five required fields:

1. Address of the resource or digital repository (URL/URI)
2. Date of creation of the digital object
3. File Name
4. Digital format
5. Producer

These allow you to maintain control of the digital object and are important for the long-term preservation of the data.

Finally, the Administrative Metadata must indicate the type of license used, as well as the legal characteristics of use and restrictions of the information that is published in a single free field.

The “Metadata Standard” document must adhere to all these guidelines and standards in order to achieve interoperability with other systems and ensure the long-term preservation of digital data. For the Cholula database, the respective metadata will be assigned for each of the files generated in each of the projects, indicating the file name, author, date and place of creation, theme or subject of the cultural asset, description, format, and unique identifier for descriptive metadata. For the metadata, the address of the digital resource or repository will be indicated using the access path of the hard drive of the computer equipment or local host of the system, the date of creation and name of the file or digital object, format in which they are found. saved the data (csv, pdf, jpg, shp), and the producer, which in this case would be the abbreviated name of the project and the year of creation: Fundamentos SIG-Cholula 2024.

Section 5: Data acquisition protocol example developed for the Urban Cholula Database

Spatial data

I.- Base Cartography

1.- Define Theme

2.- Does it exist in WMS? But

2.1: WMS = Yes -> connect -> style layer

2.2: WMS = No -> Search data group and download -> Define data: Vector or Raster

->Project to appropriate SRC -> Load to Project

II.- Drawings raised in the field

Digitization protocol:

1.- Scan to PDF

2.- Import to CAD

3.- Give 1:1 Scale properties

4.- Layout of entities

4.1: Drawings of units and elements in plan:

4.1.1 Project Area – Polygon: indicate property or complete street including sidewalks and vehicular stream

4.1.2 Footage – Polyline: indicate origin and relevant positions

4.1.3 Excavation units – Polygon: give dimensions and locate on the footage line

4.1.4 Plan elements – Polygon: element contours, pits, intrusion limits, architectural elements

4.1.5 Contents of elements in plan – Polyline: limits and detail of element, stones, sherds, bone, lithics, other artifacts and physical entities contained within the element. Each type of artifact-object-entity is drawn on a different layer

4.2: Trench profile drawings:

4.2.1 Join all the scanned sheets that make up the trench profile

4.2.2 Stratigraphic units – Polygon, indicate vertical and horizontal limits

4.2.3 Elements in profiles – Polygon, indicate element outline

4.2.4 Contents of elements in profiles – Polyline: limits and detail of element, stones, sherds, bone, lithics, other artifacts and physical entities contained within the element. Each type of artifact-object-entity is drawn on a different layer

4.3: Save in .DWG/.DXF format

5.- Editing for document (report or publication)

5.1: Select final drawing view

5.2: Give line quality and color to the entities that are going to be shown in the drawing

5.3: Place North Arrow

5.4: Place graphic scale

5.5: Place North Arrow

5.6 Place Legend according to the entities shown: line quality, hatching and color

6.- Export to .shp

6.1: Open new project, give properties, select SRC

6.2: Follow path, Project -> Import/Export -> Import layer from DWG/DXF

6.3: In the dialog box, indicate "Destination Package" name and directory of the file to import

6.4: Indicate SRC according to that used in the Cholula Database Project (WGS 84)

6.5: Select the layers you want to import, name the Group and "Accept"

7.- Editing in QGIS

7.1: Edit drawing position to match its location on the overall map

7.2: Edit attribute table to link with database tables

Uploading drawing control data to the database

Number drawings per sheet -> Extract and complete information -> Name file according to the proposed nomenclature -> upload to the database using the data entry formats

Non-spatial data

I.- Project Information

1.- Administrative data

1.1: Existing documents:

1.1.1 PDF format

1.1.2 Physical paper format = scan to PDF

2.- Field Lists

2.1: List of bags: Physical, Xlsx

2.1.1 Physical format -> upload to the database using the data entry formats

2.1.2 .xlsx format -> clean according to the established data structure -> convert to .CSV format -> import to database

2.2: List of Elements

2.2.1 Physical format -> upload to the database using the data entry formats

2.2.2 .xlsx format -> clean according to the established data structure -> convert to .CSV format -> import to database

2.2.3 Does not exist or incomplete -> Complete from list of bags, field diaries and partial and final reports -> upload to the database using the formats data entry

2.3: List of Burials

2.3.1 Physical format -> upload to the database using the data entry formats

2.3.2 .xlsx format -> clean according to the established data structure -> convert to

.CSV format -> import to database

2.3.3 Does not exist or incomplete -> Complete from list of bags, field diaries and partial and final reports -> upload to the database using the formats data entry

2.3.4 Does not exist or incomplete -> Complete from list of bags, field diaries and partial and final reports -> upload to the database using the formats data entry

2.4: List of Objects

2.4.1 Physical format -> upload to the database using the data entry formats

2.4.2 .xlsx format -> clean according to the established data structure -> convert to .CSV format -> import to database

2.4.3 Does not exist or incomplete -> Complete from list of bags, field diaries and partial and final reports -> upload to the database using the formats data entry

2.5: List of Units

2.5.1 Physical format -> upload to database using data entry formats

2.5.2 .xlsx format -> clean according to the established data structure -> convert to .CSV format -> import to database

2.5.3 Does not exist or incomplete -> Complete from list of bags, field diaries and partial and final reports -> upload to the database using the formats data entry

2.6: List of Layers

2.6.1 Physical format -> upload to the database using data entry formats

2.6.2 .xlsx format -> clean according to the established data structure -> convert to .CSV format -> import to database

2.6.3 Does not exist or incomplete -> Complete from list of bags, field diaries and partial and final reports -> upload to the database using the formats data entry

2.7: Sample List

2.7.1 Physical format -> upload to the database using the data entry formats

2.7.2 .xlsx format -> clean according to the established data structure -> convert to .CSV format -> import to database

2.7.3 Does not exist or incomplete -> Complete from list of bags, field diaries and partial and final reports -> upload to the database using the formats data entry

2.8: Box List*

2.8.1 Physical format -> upload to the database using the data entry formats

2.8.2 .xlsx format -> clean according to the established data structure -> convert to .CSV format -> import to database

2.8.3 Does not exist or incomplete -> Complete from list of bags, field diaries and partial and final reports -> upload to the database using the formats data entry

3.- Photographic archive

3.1 In digital -> Sorted by work day

3.1.1 Select 5 representative images of each type

3.1.2 Name them according to the proposed nomenclature

3.1.3 Fill out photo list

3.2 Does not exist -> Extract photos from final reports

3.2.1 Identify represented context: unit, element, profile, floor plan, general view

3.2.2 Name images according to the proposed nomenclature

3.2.3 Fill out photo list